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Annotation. A software package for human face recognition using the OpenCV technical vision library has been developed. Based on the Viola-Jones algorithm, a face is cut out from the video frame with the determination of 68 points of the face, which are used for the flexible contours method, taking into account the violation of the rules of the golden section of the natural construction of the face due to its individual asymmetry, as well as the geometric structure. Additionally, an algorithm for automatic correction of brightness and contrast of the input image is proposed. The developed software package has four options for creating a database and recognition: by a set of photos, by a recorded video stream, by an IP camera video stream, and by a USB camera video stream. The procedure for creating a base and recognition for each option is described. The article also describes the directories and files that make up the face recognition software package, and two developed modules. At the end of the article, the results of testing the software package are given.

Key words: face recognition; flexible circuits; golden section rules; facial asymmetry; color correction.

INTRODUCTION

Automatic security systems with "face control" and monitoring of unauthorized activity, robot toys and autonomous space probes, document and image analysis, video databases, self-learning computer systems, computer gesture control, application program interfaces are just some examples of the use of "computer vision" – one of the most promising research areas, which opens up new methods of interaction with a computer without the use of classical "human-

computer” interaction devices. Friendly and personalized ways to communicate with a computer means that next-generation interfaces must identify the human environment and, at a minimum, recognize him, i.e. teach a computer to identify a person's identity. There is a wide variety of biometric identification methods: voice, fingerprints, signature, retinal and iris recognition, human face [1–2]; and many of them have received wide commercial application and are used in practical and commercial developments.

Today, biometric identification methods are of great interest, which make it possible to determine the personality of a person by his physiological characteristics by recognizing by samples [3]. The classic example of biometrics is fingerprint analysis, and the latest technologies include recognition of the retina and iris. A “stop and declare yourself” interface is needed for applications with high security requirements (some delay will make the user realize the importance of the problem). Face and voice recognition technologies are best suited for intelligent environments of the generation. They are unobtrusive (recognition occurs at a distance, do not require a special level of illumination), do not restrict the user's freedom of movement [4–5].

But the most important thing, apparently, is that people usually recognize each other by faces and voices, which means that they will not experience inconvenience with a system based on similar recognition methods. Also, a new impetus to the development of face recognition systems was given by the aggravation of the situation with international terrorism. The installation of such systems in crowded places (airports, railway stations, large shopping centers) should contribute to the early identification of wanted persons.

With all the variety of different algorithms and methods of image recognition, a typical recognition method consists of three components [6]:

1. Transformation of the original image into the initial representation (may include both preprocessing and mathematical transformations, for example, calculations of principal components).

2. Identification of the key characteristics of the image (for example, the first n principal components or coefficients of the discrete cosine transform are taken).

3. Classification (modeling) mechanism: cluster model, metric, neural network, etc. Let us consider the most common used mathematical recognition methods [3], based on the geometric characteristics of the face.

MATHEMATICAL METHODS OF FACE RECOGNITION

Analysis of the geometric characteristics of the face. The essence of the method is to select a set of key points (or areas) of the face and then select a set of features. Each feature is either the distance between key points or the ratio of such distances. In contrast to the elastic graph comparison method [6], here the distances are chosen not as graph arcs, but as sets of the most informative features identified experimentally. Key points can be the corners of the eyes, lips, tip of the nose, center and others.

Method of principal components, or principal component analysis (PCA). One of the most well-known and well-developed is the principal component analysis (PCA) [3], based on the Karhunen–Loeve transformation. Active Appearance Models (AAM) and Active Shape Models (ASM)) are statistical models of images that can be adjusted to the real image by various deformations. The essence of the ASM method is to take into account the statistical relationships between the location of anthropometric points on the existing sample of face images taken from the front [6].

Method of comparison of standards. Comparison of templates (Template Matching) consists in selecting areas of the face in the image and then comparing these areas for two different images [3]. Each matched area increases the similarity score of the images. It is also one of the historically first methods for recognizing a person from a face image. To compare areas, the simplest algorithms such as pixel-by-pixel comparison of the eye image are used; rectangular areas can be used as key areas, including: eyes, nose, height, etc.

Flexible comparison with face graph. The USC system recognizes faces by comparing face graphs (elastic graph matching) [4]. DARPA and the US Army Research Laboratory have developed the Feret (face recognition technology) program [5]. The purpose of this program is to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed algorithms and stimulate the development of the best of them. During the implementation of the Feret program, several algorithms demonstrated the highest level of recognition accuracy for large databases (1200 people) in the most difficult test conditions for recognition.

Neural networks (ANN). Another direction of recognition is the use of neural networks [3]. ANN is a system of connected and interacting simple elements (artificial neurons). Each element of such a system deals only with the signals of the INS, which it periodically receives, and the signals that it periodically sends to other elements. And yet, being connected in a sufficiently large network with controlled interaction, such locally simple elements together are able to perform quite complex tasks. To train each new representation, the training parameters and other characteristics of the network must be carefully selected manually, which, however, does not guarantee convergence.

Hidden Markov Models. Markov models are a powerful tool for modeling various processes and pattern recognition [3]. By their nature, Markov models make it possible to directly take into account the spatiotemporal characteristics of signals and, therefore, have been widely used in speech recognition, and more recently in image recognition (in particular, face images).

These methods have found wide application in a number of commercial products. Let's consider some of them. The analysis carried out by the authors showed that three are the leaders - these are the developments of Viisage, Visionic, Miros [4].

Visionic's FaceIt application is based on the local feature analysis algorithm developed at the Rockefeller University [4]. A commercial company in the UK integrated FaceIt into a television anti-crime system called Mandrake [5]. This

system searches for criminals using video data from 144 cameras connected in a closed network. When an identity is established, the system informs the security officer. Visionic's FaceIt application is based on the local feature analysis algorithm developed at the Rockefeller University [4]. A commercial company in the UK integrated FaceIt into a television anti-crime system called Mandrake [5]. This system searches for criminals using video data from 144 cameras connected in a closed network. When an identity is established, the system informs the security officer.

It should be noted the development of a Russian company (Video Oko system, Russia, Skolkovo) - the system uses high-resolution black-and-white cameras for operation, the decision-making time is one and a half seconds for the Pentium 200 (registered events: movements in the frame, background changes, a face in frame, the face is recognized).

Taking into account [7] and our experience, we note the following disadvantages of these systems:

1. Low statistical significance (i.e., a high degree of deviation of the same key points of the face obtained in different shooting conditions), which reduces the recognition reliability.

2. There are special requirements for lighting in the premises where the system is installed (for example, it is not possible to register the faces of people entering from the street on a sunny day).

3. For many algorithms, the unacceptability of any external interference, such as glasses, a beard, some elements of a hairstyle.

Pic. 1. The result of the face recognition software package:

1 - input control; 2 – frame from the input stream; 3 - carved face; 4 – face found in the database.

Pic. 2. The line of the main menu of the face recognition program

4. Mandatory frontal image of the face with very small deviations (up to 15° turn to the side and 45° inclination from the frontal image).

5. Many algorithms do not take into account possible changes in facial expressions, that is, the expression must be neutral.

On pic. 1 shows the result of the face recognition program.

On pic. 2 shows the main menu bar of the face recognition software package.

During the development of the software package, some of the noted shortcomings were eliminated.

DESCRIPTION OF THE ARCHITECTURE OF THE SOFTWARE COMPLEX FOR FACE RECOGNITION.

The authors added to the algorithm of the software package the calculation of parameters using the method of flexible contours, which takes into account violations of the rules of the golden section of the natural construction of the face due to its individual asymmetry and which is based only on the geometry of the

face, due to which a high percentage of identification is achieved (for a base volume of 300 up to 400 people), low criticality of the color characteristics of the face when recognizing faces and the absence of the influence of such factors as: hiding the upper part of the face (hairstyle, headdress), eyes (glasses, except for sunglasses).

Also, the authors added to the algorithm the return of the face points to their original state, if the head of the recognized person is tilted. The authors of the article also added a correction for the brightness and contrast of the image, due to which the search for face points is performed more accurately and for this reason a greater percentage of correct recognition is achieved.

The created face recognition software package has two modes of operation:

1. Creation of base.

2. Face recognition. The face recognition software package has the following options for creating a database:

- creation of base on photos;
- creating a base on the recorded video stream;
- creating a base on the IP-camera video stream;
- creation of a database based on the video stream of a USB camera. The

face recognition software package has the following face recognition options:

- identification by photographs;
- identification by recorded video stream;
- identification by IP-camera video stream;
- Identification by the video stream of the USB camera.

The face recognition software package consists of the following files:

1. "Project1.exe" - the executable file of the face recognition software package (module 1).

2. "Detection.dll" - dynamic library of the face recognition software package (module 2).

3. "shape_predictor_68_face_landmarks.dat" is a binary file containing face point patterns.

4. "ip_path.txt" - a file containing the path to the RTSP stream of the IP camera.

The face recognition software package consists of the following directories:

1. "Gall" is a directory containing the cut out faces of the base of the face recognition software package.

2. "Sgall" - the directory in which the file "SFg.txt" is located - a file with the coordinates of the points of the base of the face recognition software package.

3. "Fgal" - the directory in which the file "fg.txt" is located - a file with vectors (vector is a mathematical model of a person's face, consisting of ten values obtained as a result of mathematical transformation of the key points of the face, - parameters and the eleventh parameter - value, which is the arithmetic mean of ten parameters) of the base of the face recognition software package.

4. "TwoFaces" - a directory that contains images-combinations of faces from the input stream and recognized faces from the base of the face recognition software package.

The face recognition software package consists of two modules:

1. Module 1 (Project1.exe) - creating a mathematical model of a face in the form of an 11-digit vector and recognition.

2. Module 2 (Detection.dll) - face search using the Viola-Jones algorithm, cutting it out and obtaining face points.

The Detection.dll library was compiled in Microsoft Visual Studio 2015 Community with the inclusion of extended instruction sets AVX (Advanced Vector Extensions - an extension of the $\times 86$ instruction set for Intel and AMD microprocessors), and the functions of the OpenCV [9] and Dlib libraries were also used.

Each module consists of the following sections of the Work Basa menu item:

1. Creation of base on photos.

2. Creation of base on the recorded video stream.
3. Creation of base on video to a stream through the IP camera.
4. Creation of base on video to a stream through the USB camera.
5. View video.
6. Derivation of the numerical model of the base.
7. Photo identification.
8. Identification by recorded video stream.
9. Identification by video stream through IP camera.
10. Identification by video stream via USB camera.
11. Stop base creation or recognition via USB or IP camera.

DESCRIPTION OF THE PROCEDURE FOR CREATING A BASE

If the base of the face recognition software package is created from photographs, then the actions are performed in the following order:

1. Press the "Load input stream" button and select the first photo from the directory that contains the database of face photos.
2. Press the menu item "Creating a database from photographs".
3. Press the menu item "Create database".

If the base of the face recognition software package is created from the recorded video stream, then the following steps are performed:

1. Move the video from which the base will be created to the same directory where the face recognition software package is located, with the name "1_Rec.mp4".
2. Press the menu item "Creating a database from a recorded video stream".
3. Press the menu item "Create database".

If the base of the face recognition software package is created based on the video stream of the IP camera, then the following steps are performed:

1. Specify the path to the RTSP stream of the IP camera, through which the base of the face recognition software package will be created, in the file

“ip_path.txt”, which is located in the same directory as the executable file of the face recognition software package.

2. Click the menu item "Creating a database by video stream through an IP camera".

3. Click the menu item "Stop creating a database or recognition via USB or IP camera" after cutting faces from the IP camera stream (when it is necessary to complete the process of cutting faces, the user of the face recognition software package decides for himself).

4. Press the menu item "Create database".

If the base of the face recognition software package is created using a video stream via a USB camera, then the following steps are performed:

1. Click the menu item "Creating a database by video stream via USB camera".

2. Press the button "Stop creating a base or recognition via USB or IP camera" after cutting faces from the USB camera stream (when it is necessary to complete the process of cutting faces, the user of the face recognition software package decides for himself).

3. Press the menu item "Create database".

DESCRIPTION OF THE PROCEDURE FOR FACE RECOGNITION

If face recognition will be carried out using photographs, then the following steps are performed:

1. Click the "Load Gall database" button and select the first photo from the Gall directory, which is located in the same directory as the executable file of the face recognition program.

2. Press the menu item "Output of the numerical model of the base".

3. Press the "Load input stream" button and select the first photo from the directory that contains the database of face photos to be recognized.

4. Press the menu item "Identification by photographs".

If face recognition will be carried out according to the recorded video, then the actions are performed in the following order:

If face recognition will be carried out using photographs, then the following steps are performed:

1. Click the "Load Gall database" button and select the first photo from the Gall directory, which is located in the same directory as the executable file of the face recognition program.

2. Press the menu item "Output of the numerical model of the base".

3. Press the "Load input stream" button and select the first photo from the directory that contains the database of face photos to be recognized.

4. Press the menu item "Identification by photographs".

If face recognition will be carried out according to the recorded video, then the actions are performed in the following order:

2. Press the menu item "Output of the numerical model of the base".

3. Write the path to the RTSP stream of the IP camera through which face recognition will be performed in the file "ip_path.txt", which is located in the same directory as the executable file of the face recognition software package.

4. Press the menu item "Identification by video stream through an IP camera".

5. Click the button "Stop base creation or recognition via USB or IP camera" after face recognition from the IP camera stream is completed (it is up to the user of the face recognition software package to decide when it is necessary to complete the face recognition process).

If face recognition will be carried out via a video stream via a USB camera, then the following steps are performed:

1. Press the "Load Gall base" button and select the first photo from the Gall directory, which is located in the same directory as the executable file of the face recognition software package.

2. Press the menu item "Output of the numerical model of the base".

3. Press the menu item "Identification by video stream via USB camera".

4. Click the button "Stop base creation or recognition via USB or IP camera" after face recognition from the IP camera stream is completed (it is up to the user of the face recognition software package to decide when it is necessary to complete the face recognition process).

The face recognition software package runs on Windows 7 × 64, Windows 8.1 × 64 operating systems, and its testing was carried out on computers with Intel Xeon, Intel i5, Intel i7 processors.

Conditions for testing the face recognition software package:

1. A database was created from the video stream (faces with dots were cut out) of 385 people.

2. A verification test video stream was created, consisting of 385 of the same faces as in the database, 118 faces included in the list of 385 people, but on a different day, and 100 faces of strangers not included in the list of 385 people.

3. A total of 603 people were passed through the program.

The results of testing the face recognition software package:

1. All 385 people are recognized from the input stream.

2. All duplicates of 118 people were found and recognized as being included in the database.

3. Strangers were found in the amount of 100 people.

4. The recognition time per object was 479 milliseconds.

CONCLUSION

This article presents the description and results of the developed face recognition program, which has the following features:

1. A high percentage of identification (for a database of 300 to 400 people).

2. No influence of such factors as: hiding the upper part of the face (hairstyle, headdress), eyes (glasses, except for sunglasses) and head tilt.

3. The person recognition time is (in the software package used) 479 milliseconds for a base of 385 people and a flow of 603 people.

4. To determine the points in the Viola-Jones algorithm, the color characteristics of the face are not very critical (the proposed RGB recognition algorithm does not use pixels).

5. In the created software package, the correction of the brightness and contrast of the image is implemented (if the image has low brightness and contrast, then it increases) to improve the accuracy of recognition.

Further directions of research should be directed to:

- improvement of recognition taking into account the rotation and inclination of the head;

- compensation of influence of brightness and contrast;

- determination of the optimal number of key face parameters.

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